

ONLINE COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES: CHALLENGES AND GUIDELINES

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Research Paper

Abstract

The advancement in Information Technology has influenced human life in several ways. Online communication is one of the interesting aspects of this advancement, which has not only facilitated communication between two persons sitting miles away, but also significantly contributed in various professional and academic activities such as online learning. Online learning offers a wide range of benefits which makes it unique from the conventional teaching. One of the prominent features of online learning is that the communication between an instructor and a student is not bounded by time and space. It means a student has the convenience to learn in a ubiquitous environment with the flexibility to participate in an online course while staying in any region of the world. The experts in online learning agree upon the fact that online learning is more student centric as compared to teacher centric, in which students need to actively collaborate with each other to increase their learning (Barab, Kling, & Gray, 2004; Pierce, 2003; Weiss, Knowlton, & Speck, 2000).

Keeping in mind the benefits of online learning, yet there are several challenges faced in online learning. In order to facilitate the online collaborations, it is very common to use online learning platforms that encourage group discussion and group projects. In face-to-face learning, as practiced in conventional learning approach, the student assessment is done in different ways, where a teacher can directly observe a student and his/her participation in group activities. However, in online learning, a teacher cannot directly observe a student, which needs different grading criteria as compared to conventional teaching.

Heejung et-al., (2008) carried out a social experiment to determine the key factors of online groupwork, both positive and negative. Although the number of participants was low, none were students, all were based in the USA, cultural issues were not considered, wide time zone differences were not experienced, group sizes were unequal, gender spread was male biased, no report on how many questionnaires were submitted that were used to create results, the outcome was a set of issues that basically concur with more robust similar study from Bryk, Gomez, & Grunow (2011), which also aligns with practical experience.

In this paper, the details of a study that was carried out in the computer science education over several semesters are presented. The study reports on findings about a course run in parallel both in online form and on location as frontal course with physical presence. The paper reports on certain challenges that emerged especially during online group activities. Challenges encountered in managing online groups as well as some other issues involved in group generated projects are also discussed.

Like research seems to support, the classroom environment is a powerful determinant of persistence in science and technology domain, especially for women students. Some of the results from the experiments that were carried out hint at the fact that environmental factors can also play an important role in student learning behaviors and performance. Beside innovative classroom strategies, other factors seem to influence successful teaching. Among these, the attitude of the teacher is important as well. Learning outcome may also be enhanced when the teacher tailors class activities to match the pace of student learning, their knowledge and when the teacher actively engages them in the learning process. The analysis of the data collected in class for both online and on-campus students provides interesting insights about issues on online teaching. After a discussion of common issues and problems encountered while teaching the courses, this paper ends with the presentation of a list of guidelines that I propose for online groupwork management and organization. These guidelines are based entirely on the experience gathered running these courses. When these guidelines were followed, the drop-out rate in the online course resulted up to 30% lower than the drop-out rate of the same course run in parallel with students with on campus presence.

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